

ROLE OF KETHU IN HINDU ASTROLOGY

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Abstract:

In this paper the characters of Kethu and the professions influenced by Kethu are explained. Yogam given by Kethu and Dosham given by Kethu are detailedly explained. Kethu standing house from lagna to twelfth house predictions are given elaborately. According to Pulippani astrology predictions of Kethu standing bhava, from lagna to twelfth bhava are given exactly.

Key Words: Characters of Kethu - Professions given by Kethu - Yogam by Kethu - Dosham by Kethu - Saturn with Kethu - Kethu standing house and prediction - prediction of Kethu standing bhava according to Pulippani astrology.

Characters of Kethu:

Kethu is the serpent planet. It is called as red snake. It moves reverse direction. It represents divinity, spiritualism, divorce, separation, vinayaga upasana, holy saints and pilgrimages.

Kethu in First Bhava (Lagna):

It is not auspicious. If the ascendent is scorpio, capricorn or Aquaris, Kethu gives positive results. Above three ascendent people should come the top most leader of the world.

Kethu in Second Bhava:

It spoils ones primary education but the later education of the native would be bright.

Kethu in Third Bhava:

It is called Upajayasthana, The native lives happily. He/She is worshipped as the honourable person by all. But the native would be tortured by his/her brothers.

Kethu in Fourth Bhava:

The native should be selfish. He/She should never listen others words. The native has bad habits and bad characters. The native never respects others.

Kethu in Fifth Bhava:

The native should be addicted by alcohol. The native has poor and bad characters. This place is not favour for one's children.

Kethu in Sixth Bhava:

It is called upajayasthana. The native lives happily. They are worshipped by the society but they have worst thoughts.

Kethu in Seventh Bhava:

It collapses one's family life. The native may intercourse with lot of people. Divorce and separation is the normal one for them.

Example Chart:

Date of birth : 21.5.1982
 Time of birth : 7.42 am
 Birth star : Aswini
 Ascendent : Gemini
 Place of Birth : Kumbakonam

Venus	Moon	Sun Mercury	ASC Rahu	Mars	Rahu	8	Moon
9	D1 RASI		2	Sun Venus	D 9 NAVAMSA		Mercury Saturn
8			3	4			11
Kethu	6	Jupiter	Mars Saturn	Jupiter	2	ASC Kethu	12

Kethu dasa balane: 3 Years 4 months 15 days

In this horoscope kethu stands in seventh house. The native lived with his spouse only two years. Later they got divorce.

Kethu In Eighth Bhava:

Kethu in eighth house give more illegal contacts. The native should be rich in wealth but poor in health.

Example Chart:

Date of Birth : 21.11.1992
 Time of Birth : 05.08 am
 Birth Star : Hastham
 Ascendent : Libra
 Place of Birth : Villuppuram

6	7	Kethu	9	Rahu ASC	2	Jupiter	Saturn
5	D1 RASI		Mars	12	D 9 NAVAMSA		Moon
Saturn			11	11			Mars Sun Venus
Venus	Sun Mercur Rahu	ASC	Jupiter Moon	10	9	8	Mercury Kethu

Moon dasa balane : 1 Year 5 months 10 days

In this horoscope the native is a womanizer. He intercoursed with more than hundred ladies and finally he died by AIDS.

Kethu in Nineth Bhava:

If Kethu stands ninth house in horoscope, The native always hates his/her father. The native has no faith in god. The native has best friends.

Kethu in Tenth Bhava:

If kethu standing in tenth house in horoscope the native is an artiste. Fame always come. The native should be an expert. The native has smooth touch in society.

Kethu in Eleventh Bhava:

If Kethu stands in eleventh house it is called upajayasthana. The health of the native is well. The native has also wealth. They earn lot of properties.

Example Chart:

Date of birth : 08.01.1968
 Time of birth : 05.08 am
 Birth star : Revathi
 Ascendent : Sagittarius
 Place of Birth : Vellore

Moon Saturn	Rahu	6	7	Moon	Rahu ASC	2	3
Mars	D1 RASI		8	11	D 9 NAVAMSA		Jupiter
2			Jupiter	10			5
Mercury Sun ASC	Venus	Kethu	10	Mercury	Sun Venus Mars	Kethu Saturn	6

Moon dasa balane: 3 Years 1 month 22 days

In this horoscope kethu stands in eleventh house, the native is sound in financial status. He has lot of properties in the heart of the city.

Kethu in Twelfth Bhava:

If kethu stands in twelveth house the native's soul would go to the heaven after death. The native do only good karmas.

Predictions According to Pulippani Astrology:

Kethu in First Bhava (Lagna):

If Kethu stands in lagna bhava the native's colour is black and his/her face looks always dull. The native is a sick fellow and take medicine regularly.

Kethu in Second Bhava:

If Kethu stands in Second bhava the native is a cunning person. He/she is always enemy for his/her relatives. The native should earn money from their profession.

Kethu in Third Bhava:

If Kethu stands in third house the native should always brave. The native has wisdom. But the native has disease in his/her skull.

Kethu in Fourth Bhava:

If Kethu stands in fourth house the native's home would be spoilt. The native's mother's health condition is so poor. This position is not good for mother.

Example Chart:

Date of birth : 22.12.2000
 Time of birth : 11.59 pm
 Birth star : Anuradha
 Ascendent : Virgo
 Place of Birth : Trichy

7	8	Saturn Jupiter	Rahu
6	D1 RASI		11
Venus			12
Kethu Sun Mercury	Moon	Mars	ASC

Jupiter	Rahu	Mercury	Sun
2	D 9 NAVAMSA		Venus
ASC Saturn			Moon
12	Mars	Kethu	9

Saturn dasa balance: 17 Years 6 months 23 days

In this horoscope the natives mother expired at his age of 5.

Kethu in Fifth Bhava:

If Kethu stands in fifth house the native is a very cunning one. The native always has fear about his/her health. The native's child would die.

Kethu in Sixth Bhava:

If Kethu stands in sixth house the native is an VIP. The native has name and fame. The native easily win his/her enemies. The native has always good health.

Kethu in Seventh Bhava:

If Kethu stands in seventh house the native has intercourse with lot of people. The native is always lazy. The family life of the native is very poor one. Divorce and separation are easily done.

Kethu in Eighth Bhava:

If Kethu stands in eighth house the native will be affected by snake. The native wants to cheat other's properties. The death of the native is very cruel.

Example Chart:

Date of birth : 22.12.1972
 Time of birth : 04.27 am
 Birth star : Punarvasu
 Ascendent : Scorpio
 Place of Birth : Kovilpatti

5	6	Saturn	Kethu Moon
4	D1 RASI		9
3			10
Rahu Jupiter Sun	Mars ASC Venus Mercury	12	11

7	8	Kethu	Sun Moon
6	D 9 NAVAMSA		Mars Saturn
5			12
Mercury	Rahu	Venus Jupiter	ASC

Jupiter dasa balance: 06 Years 1 month 3 days

In this horoscope kethu stands in eighth house. The native was killed by his enemies at the age of 32.

Kethu in Ninth Bhava:

If Kethu stands in ninth house the native is a wealthy one and also has a rowdy character. The native always has angry.

Kethu in Tenth Bhava:

If Kethu stands in tenth house the native has physical strength and wisdom. The native has lot of money but sick in health. The native is hated by the society.

Kethu in Eleventh Bhava:

If Kethu stands in eleventh house, the native has good physical structure. The native has wealth and happy. The native also get happiness from his/her child.

Kethu in Twelfth Bhava:

If Kethu stands in twelfth house the native's eyes and feet are affected. The native is attacked by paralysis. The native loss his/her own wealth.

Saturn with Kethu Conjunctions:

This conjunction is favour for siddha doctors, astrologers, philosophers healers and lawyers.

Yogas by Kethu:

Mukthi Yogam:

If Kethu stands in twelveth bhava one should enter the heaven after his/her death So, It is called mukthi yogam.

Paradise Yogam:

If Kethu conjunctions with saturn there is no re birth. The native will go to paradise directly after his/her death.

Royal Spouse Yogam:

If Kethu stands in Taurus, Libra or Pisces with Venus and it comes Seventh bhava from the ascendent the native's spouse would be very royal with more wealth (Properties and Jewels).

Kethu Professions:

Religious conversion, drugs, alcohol, flesh, spiritual, Computer engineers, Website making, Rope related business.

Conclusion:

Role of Kethu in Indian astrology takes a vital part. Though Kethu is a shadow planet and also has no own house. It's position in our horoscope is very important. During the marriage matching Kethu plays an important role. We should worship Karpaga Vinayagar and Anjaneyar (Hanuman) to reduce the evil effects of Kethu.

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